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Sustainability Disclosure and Financial Performance of Oil and Gas Marketing Companies in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of sustainability disclosure on financial performance of listed oil and gas marketing firms in Nigeria. The population of the study is made up of the 13 listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study considered using net profit margin, return on asset and return on capital as proxies for financial performance. Secondary data collection was used for the study. Data in relation to sustainability disclosure and financial performance were collected from the firm's annual reports as well as standalone sustainability reports. Data for the study were analysed using STATA 13 statistical software. The regression coefficients, Z-values, and p-values from three regression models investigating the relationship between sustainability disclosure (SUSD) and three financial metrics. The results indicate a significant positive association between sustainability disclosure and both NPM and ROA, as evidenced by the coefficients (0.153) with corresponding z-values (2.16) and low p-values (0.002). However, the coefficient (0.016) for ROCE. The study therefore, recommends among others that, firms in the oil and gas sector should emphasize more on reporting their sustainability performance as it is capable of improving their financial performance.

Keywords: Financial Disclosure, Firm Performance, Sustainability, STATA

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The concept of sustainability emerged out of fear of the present and future impact resulting from resource utilization for human development on the environment. The fear in terms of water, land and air pollution, land and resource depletion, degradation, and deforestation, have combined and led to a new paradigm for resource utilization aimed at meeting the present human need without compromising the future needs of such resources by the future generations. Historically, the concept of sustainability has been a man's civilization companion from the Roman civilization to the medieval period, pre- and post-Christian era to modern western European civilization, up to the industrial revaluation of the 18th century, which saw a great demand for raw materials as a result of expansion in industries and modes of production. The revaluation has come at a cost to the environment in the form of depletion and deterioration of natural resources and the ecosystem, which has raised concerns about long-term sustainability (Renato et al., 2018).

The earlier sustainability effort was in the form of environmental protection and resource depletion; for example, a German mining engineer published a paper on the negative impact of wood cutting on wildlife and mining activities in Europe, and Hans Carl von Cleve coined the term "sustainability" in the German

Forestry Department in 1713 to strike a balance between cutting older trees and growing new ones for future benefits.

The industrial disasters such as; US nuclear catastrophe of 1979, Exxon Valdez Alaska oil spill in 1989, the Bhopal chemical accident India in 1984, Chernobyl in Ukraine 1986, the Kuwait Gulf War Oil Fire in 1991, Gulf of Mexico Deep water Oil Spill 2010 and several other disasters around the world have combined, shifted and continue to shift the focus of attention toward environmental accounting and reporting in 1980s, 1990s upward to 2000s. Similarly, at the same time, the concept of Negative Screening, which has gained traction in the United Kingdom (UK) and the United States, converts firms' social performance scores into numbers, allowing socially or environmentally conscious investors to avoid companies that do not meet environmental or social requirements in addition to their financial goals (Uwakonye et al., 2018)

Financial performance is a description of a company's financial health over time as measured by capital coverage, liquidity, and profitability indices. Financial performance may be measured by looking at a company's financial parameters, and one of the ways to do so is to look at its profitability. In a business, the most crucial factor is profitability. Performance in practically every aspect of human life has recently attracted more attention. Performance is a subjective notion that may be divided into many categories based on its nature. The concept of performance is multifaceted. Various academics, educators, researchers, and intellectuals have conceptualized performance from various perspectives. Shen (2017), for example, saw performance as both a means to a goal and an end result. Similarly, Performance is the capacity to distinguish the end effects of organizational operations.

Performance, according to Oyedokun et al., (2018), is an organization's meaningful outcomes after efficiently employing various constrained resources. Furthermore, he asserted that performance does not refer to the conclusion or outcome of an activity, but rather to the path taken. It is possible to evaluate the level of a company's financial performance by using a variety of different financial indicators, such as return on asset (ROA), TOBIN's Q, Return On Investment (ROI), Return On Equity (ROE), Earnings Per Share (EPS), Market Share (MS), Revenue Growth (RG), and cost merit. Some of the indicators that should be looked for when measuring performance in non-financial or market-based areas include growth in market share and sales, satisfaction among customers and employees, organizational survival and stability, risk management, stakeholder management, risk management, and productivity, relational and social capital, and behavioural performance. The study measured the financial performance using Net Profit Margin, return on Asset and Return on Capital Employed.

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

There are several sustainability performance implications for oil and gas companies. According to PricewaterhouseCoopers (2014), international oil companies have more significant onshore assets; they are concerned about the repercussions that government payments in the form of tax and community development levies have on current and future earnings. However, there are implications of the operations of a business on people and the planet. In the view of Ramirez and Gonzalez (2013), the awareness of these implications has resulted in the inclusion of sustainability reports in financial information. When these implications are taken into consideration, they could have a less negative impact on future earnings. As noted in Idachaba (2011), the oil and gas industry operator aim to maximize production at minimal costs using state of the art technology. One of the issues that can reduce costs is sustainable performance regarding a company's relationship with people, the planet, and profits. In the history of sustainability reporting, oil and gas companies have reported more after an adverse event such as a spill has occurred. Patten (1992) finds that oil companies increase their environmental disclosures in annual reports after the Exxon Valdez oil spill in 1989. Similarly, Deegan et al. (2000) note a change in disclosure practices after certain events, including the Exxon Valdez oil spill and the Bhopal disaster. These findings align with the legitimacy school of thought, where companies report to defend or maintain their image in society. Adverse events such as oil spills result in bad publicity, influencing stakeholders' perceptions concerning the company. Sustainability disclosures are still evolving, as shown in prior studies. Even when companies are within countries that require mandatory reporting, adherence is primarily influenced by their individual decision to report except where there are sanctions for not reporting. Some studies have

also argued that sustainability reporting is synonymous with developed countries globally, such as Germany, Denmark, Sweden, South Africa, the United Kingdom, the United States of America, France, and Malaysia. Therefore, this is because these countries understand the need for such reporting and can carry them out.

Regulation and monitoring of sustainability reporting by companies is a crucial issue for advancements in sustainability reporting. Regulators such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and industry regulators can make it mandatory for interim sustainability reports to be filed by companies. Although there are arguments that regulation alone is insufficient to make companies engage in a particular reporting practice. However, there is no stock market policy from ethical investors for oil companies in Nigeria to report sustainability, there are sustainability disclosure requirements from the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) in Nigeria. This NSE development implies that companies, especially environmentally-sensitive companies, will comply with the SEC's disclosure requirements to avoid sanctions. The development of sustainable development related to stock markets shows that market-based policies are essential to engender companies' commitment to improved sustainability performance. For instance, the stock market could improve corporate sustainability performance through ethical or socially responsible investors.

A large body of academic literature has examined the sustainability disclosure and financial performance in both advanced and developing countries characterised by mixed findings because most of the results of the studies is either significant or not significant such as (Xue, et al., 2021; Felix & Idowu 2021; Kalagbor, et al., 2021; Ordu, & Amah 2021; Giron et.al., 2020; Miaad, 2020; Angga & Dodik 2020; Omesi & Berembo 2020; Igbru et al., 2020) similarly, most of the studies Abdulrahman, et al., (2021) have been conducted up until the year 2021 but only utilizing data relating to years to the year 2019. No study has made use of data relating to the most current available financial year end annual reports. This study covered period of 2010-2022 thereby filling the time gap

1.3 Research Questions

The following are the research questions which would be provided answers to at the end of the study:

- i. What is the impact between Sustainability Disclosure and Net Profit Margin (NPM) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the impact between Sustainability Disclosure and Return on Assets (ROA) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The following specific were developed from the research questions:

- i. To evaluate the impact of Sustainability Disclosure on the Net profit margin (NPM) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria.
- ii. To determine the impact of Sustainability Disclosure on the Return on Assets (ROA) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria.

The following hypotheses were developed from the research objectives:

Ho1 Sustainability Disclosure has no significant impact with Net Profit Margin (NPM) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria.

Ho2 Sustainability Disclosure has no significant impact with Return on Assets (ROA) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria.

2.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

According to GRI (2019), sustainability reporting is the practice of measuring, disclosing and being accountable to internal and external stakeholders to achieve the goals of sustainable development. Similarly, Umoren and Ukpung (2022) define sustainability accounting as the sub branch of accounting which handles the activities, methods and systems of the business to record, analyse and report first, the financial effects caused by environmental and social factors and second, the ecological and social effects of a defined economic system. It is not just reported generation from collected data; instead, it is a method to internalize and improve an organization's commitment to sustainable development in a way that can be demonstrated to both internal and external stakeholders.

According to Akpan and Simeon (2021), define sustainability reporting as way of making these disclosures, companies make stakeholders aware of how they are integrating the principles of sustainable development into their organizational goals and daily operations. Effiong, et al., (2019) define as a holistic framework for reporting the tripartite performance dimensions of firms. A lot of reasons have been advanced toward companies' triple bottom line reporting. Among such reasons is the fact that managers believe that it is economically rational to give back to the society and environment from which they draw economic resources and that the economic benefits from disclosures might offset any associated costs accompanying non-disclosures. Asaolu et al., (2011) defined the term sustainability reporting or "triple bottom-line" is a framework for measuring and reporting corporate performance against economic, social, and environmental parameters. This is due to the fact that, as was already said, sustainability reporting is believed to increase both the organization's acceptability within the sector in which it operates and the transparency between the organisation and its stakeholders (Ordu and Amah, 2021).

2.2 Concept of Financial Performance

Commercial performance, sometimes referred to as profitability, is a factor in determining the competency and efficacy of an organization's operations. Dwivedi (2002) asserts that there are two categories of performance: financial and non-financial. Financial performance is concerned with traits that are closely related to the financial report. Financial performance, according to Dwivedi (2002), is a subjective evaluation of how well a business can generate revenue using the resources available to it via its primary operating system. The term is also used to refer to a broad indicator of a company's overall financial health over time, and it may be used to both direct and indirect comparisons of industries or sectors (Dwivedi, 2002).

Wang (2002). Performance pointers similar as Return on capital employed (ROCE), ROA, Net profit, Net profit periphery, ROE and tip per share, Earnings per share, have been used by former studies (Dwivedi, 2002; Uwigbe and Egbide; 2012, Zayol, Agaregh and Enerji, 2017; Adewoye) to measures performance of enterprises, especially in the oil painting and gas operations hence this study adopts ROCE and Net profit for performance. Additionally, it has been emphasised that CSR conditioning must take into account the host communities, employees, and government as stakeholders (Bhattacharya et al., 2009; Imran, et al., 2010).

2.3 Return on Asset (ROA)

Return on Assets (ROA) is one of profitability ratios. In the analysis of financial statements, this ratio is most often highlighted, because it is able to indicate company success to create profits. ROA is able to measure the company ability to generate profits in the past to then be projected in the future. Assets in question are overall company properties, obtained from the capital itself or from foreign capital that has been converted into capital that has been converted into company assets used for corporate sustainability. According to Brigham and Houston (2001), return on asset (ROA) is calculated by comparing available net profit for common shareholders to total assets.

2.4 Net Profit Margin (NPM)

The goal of every business organization is to make profit (Nimalathasm, 2009). Thus profitability, referred to the ability of a firm to make profit. A business operation that is not profitable in a long run may not survival. Profitability is defined by Pandey, (1980) as the ability of a business operation, although it infers the word profit in relative to other components.

However, profit margin is the ratio helps in measuring the relationship between sales and operating profit. It measures the profit made on sales after all the running expenses have been deducted from the gross profit.

2.5 Empirical Review

Girón et al., (2020) examined Sustainability Reporting and enterprises' profitable Performance substantiation from Asia and Africa with the thing of determining the factors that impact the relinquishment of new sustainability reporting and external assurance procedures. Data was gathered from

the Sustainability Disclosure Database and the Orbis database, and statistical analysis was performed using retrogression.

Malarvizhi and Ranjanni (2016) investigate if there is a causal link between corporate environmental disclosure (CED) and the financial performance of a subset of Indian firms registered on the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE). To build an environmental disclosure index (EDI) and evaluate theories on the connection between company performance and environmental disclosure, they use content analysis techniques. The instrument utilised to collect primary data was a questionnaire. With EDI as the dependent variable and Net Profit Margin (NPM), and as the independent variables, the data for this research was analysed using a regression model. The results show that there is no relationship between company performance and environmental disclosure. They recommended educating firms about the advantages of improved environmental performance and enforcing compliance with the requirements for long-term survival. Environmental governance should involve government teaching on moral environmental disclosure at the social and educational levels.

Raymond et al., (2016) evaluated the impact of sustainable accounting measures on business organisations' performance in Nigeria. Time series data were used, together with an ex post facto study methodology. The company's annual reports and financial statements for Nigeria were used to gather data for the research. Using SPSS Version 20.0, regression analysis was used to examine the hypotheses that had been developed. Based on the data, the study concluded that environmental costs have a favourable influence on business organizations' ability to generate profits in Nigeria but have a negative impact on their ability to generate revenue. On the basis of this, the researcher suggests that Indigenous and multinational enterprises make sure that stringent environmental accounting principles are followed in order to guarantee steady organizational performance.

3.0 Theoretical Review

3.1 Legitimacy Theory

Suchman (1995) defined legitimacy theory as an overarching viewpoint or premise that is desirable, acceptable, or relevant to a certain institution. All of the engagements must have some publically determined standards, values, beliefs, and purpose. Crosman (2013) defined legitimation as the process through which a community structure or trait becomes accepted. Legitimacy theory, according to Deegan and Unerman (2011), is based on the idea that there is a "social compact" between a firm and society in its activities. Besides that, Deegan, (2002). The social contract, according to him, is a set of expectations that society has about how a firm conducts business. Legitimacy theory can assess the firms that embrace environmental and social responsibility reporting, according to Deegan, (2002); Deegan & Blomquist, (2006); O'Donovan, (2002). This is done to legitimate company operations when societal norms and expectations for corporate entities change, or when corporations are confronted with violations of current societal norms and expectations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Research Design

The research design adopted by this study is the longitudinal and ex-post research facto research designs. The justification for suitability of the designs is based on the fact that the data for the study is historical in nature, cuts across several years and companies and the study established the relationship between variables. The study is longitudinal in nature, as it involves outlook of financial performance over a range of five years (2010-2022). For the purpose of analyzing the data, descriptive statistics was used to calculate median, median, standard deviation, variance, maximum, minimum, skewness, and kurtosis which will help to explain or summarized data in a meaningful way. Correlation is used to establish the relationship between dependent and independent variables, while regression analysis is used to test the study's hypotheses. The dependent variable, financial performance was measure by Net profit, and Return on Assets while sustainability disclosure check list was uses as a proxy to measure sustainability disclosure. The STATA 13.0 software was used to analyzed the data collected.

4.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study is the entire oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria listed on the Nigeria Exchange Website (2020).

Listed Oil and Gas Marketing Companies in Nigeria

S/N	Oil and Gas Marketing companies in nigeria	Listed date
1	TOTAL OIL	JULY 1ST 1956
2	MOBIL OIL	25TH JULY, 1951
3	OANDO OIL	NOVEMBER, 2005
4	FORTE OIL	JULY 2ND 2014
5	ETERNAL OIL	1ST AUGUST, 1998
6	ANINO OIL	15TH MAY, 1981
7	CONOIL	JANUARY 1ST, 1989
8	SEPLAT OIL	DECEMBER 31ST, 2019
9	CAVERTON	20TH MAY, 2014
10	CAPITAL OIL	31ST OCTOBER, 2022
11	RAJUNITY OIL	21ST MARCH, 1989
12	MRS OIL NIGERIA PLC	JULY 14TH, 2021
13	JAPPAUL OIL AND MARITIME SERVICES	21ST JUNE, 2023

Source: Nigeria Exchange Website (2020)

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Model Specification

There are two variables in this study; Sustainability disclosure and Profitability. Sustainability disclosure is the independent variable, while Profitability is the dependent variables. The dimensions for the independent variables and the measures of dependent variable are as follows:

The Dependent Variables: These include NPM, ROA which would be used as proxies for financial performance.

4.3 The independent variables employed in the study is Sustainability disclosure and would be proxied by sustainability reporting check list for sustainability disclosure which was employed to see if companies disclose certain information in annual reports or sustainability report (Marston & Shrides, 1991). A disclosure index has been used by several scholars to examine the reporting practices of various components. The GRI-based sustainability disclosure index utilised in this study is made up of a long list of 99 elements that are relevant to a wide spectrum of users.

The functional relationship between the dependent and independent variables in this study could be stated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 FP &= F(SD) \text{-----} (1) \\
 NPV &= \alpha + \beta_1(SUS)_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \text{.....(ii)} \\
 ROA &= \alpha + \beta_1(SUS)_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \text{-----(iii)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where:

- FP=Finance
- SD=Sustainability Disclosure
- NPM= Net profit margin
- ROA=Return on Assets

Variables of the Study and their Measurement

Variable	Measuring Tools	Prior Studies that used same
Independent Variable		
Sustainability Disclosure (Independent Variable)	This measured by using sustainability disclosure check list. (Appendix II)	Othman & Mo'taz (2019), Igbru (2020), Miaad (2020),
Dependent variables		
Net Profit Margin (NPM)	$NPM = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Sales}}$	Laskar (2019), Usman & Amran (2015), Khan Et Al., (2015), Nwobu (2015),
Return on Asset (ROA)	$ROA = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Average Total Assets}}$	Malarvizhi & Ranjanni (2016), Ironkwe & Ordu (2016)

4.4 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistics:

	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Skewness	kurtosis
NPM	0.014	0.067	-0.199	0.166	-0.929	4.26
ROA	0.008	0.036	-0.101	0.132	0.435	5.32
SUSD	0.425	0.109	0.027	0.557	-1.529	6.309

Source: Author's Computation using Stata13 Output, (2023)

Table above provides the descriptive statistics for both explanatory and explained variables in this study. The average net profit margin, as illustrated in the table, is 0.014, accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.06, signifying substantial variability among the selected listed firms in Nigeria. The minimum and maximum values are -N0.199 and N0.166, respectively. The Return on Assets (ROA) is reflected in an average of N0.08. ROA serves as a metric gauging the efficiency of stockholders' invested capital by measuring the contribution of net income per Naira (local currency) invested by the firms. The minimum and maximum ROA values are -0.101 and 0.132, respectively. This implies that the most profitable firms earned N0.13 of net income from a single Naira of asset investment, while the maximum losses incurred were -N0.101 on each Naira of asset investment. The substantial standard deviation of ROA at 0.036 indicates significant variability among the sampled firms

The return on capital employed (ROCE) is calculated as the ratio of net operating income to capital employed. During the study span, the average of return on capital employed across the sampled listed firms in Nigeria was 2.4%, with a standard deviation of about 7.2%. The ROCE has a minimal ratio of -18.8% and maximum value of 19.9% respective.

Looking at the mean of SUSD (0.425) presented in Table 4.1, it indicates that the mean SUSD is 35.7%. It represents the fact that the average SUSD over the investigation duration was deemed to be low. Furthermore, the highest SUSD disclosure is 55.7%, while the lowest disclosure is 2.7%, showing a wide range of SUSD activities across the sample firms. This discovery may be the result of studying a diverse group of businesses of various sizes and degrees of environmental awareness. Since the standard variance of 0.12 is not far from the average, it suggests that there is little variation within the companies sampled.

Summary of the Hypotheses

	Coefficient	Z-value	P-value	Decision
NPM=> SUSD	.153	6.98	.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
ROA=> SUSD	.00034	6.84	.000	Reject Null Hypothesis

4.5 Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Sustainability Disclosure has no relationship with Net Profit Margin (NPM) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria.

The findings from Table 4.6 indicate a substantial positive impact of sustainability disclosure (SUSD) on net profit margin (NPM). This is statistically supported by a coefficient of 0.153 and a p-value of 0.000, both significant at the 5% level. This suggests that sustainability disclosure significantly influences the net profit margin of listed oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria. Consequently, in light of these results, the study rejects the null hypothesis that sustainability disclosure has no relationship with the net profit margin (NPM) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Sustainability Disclosure has no significant relationship with Return on Assets (ROA) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria.

The outcomes from Table above reveal a positive and significant impact of sustainability disclosure on the return on assets (ROA) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria. This is evidenced by a coefficient of 0.00034, coupled with a p-value of 0.00, which is below the 5% significance level. Thus, sustainability disclosure is shown to have a positive and significant influence on return on assets. In light of these results, the study rejects the null hypothesis, which posited that sustainability disclosure has no significant relationship with the return on assets (ROA) of oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria

5.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

5.1 Sustainability Disclosure and Net Profit Margin (NPM)

The results from Table above indicate a positive and significant relationship between sustainability disclosure and net profit margin. Companies that disclose their sustainability performance seem to experience higher net profit margins, suggesting a correlation between sustainability practices and financial success. This positive relationship can be attributed to the cost-saving and efficiency-enhancing benefits of sustainability initiatives. Measures such as waste reduction, improved energy efficiency, and effective supply chain management contribute to increased profitability. This finding aligns with the proposition of agency theory, which suggests that sustainability practices influence financial performance. It is also consistent with the results reported by Felix and Idowu (2021). However, it contradicts the findings of Malarvizhi and Ranjanni (2016).

5.2 Sustainability Disclosure and Return on Asset (ROA)

The study's findings reveal a positive and significant relationship between sustainability disclosure and return on assets (ROA). This suggests that an increase in sustainability disclosure is associated with an improvement in return on assets. The connection stems from the role of sustainability disclosure in fostering stronger relationships with stakeholders. Companies, by openly sharing their sustainability practices and performance, showcase their dedication to environmental, social, and governance (ESG) considerations, addressing risks and seizing opportunities in these areas. This, in turn, builds trust and confidence among customers, employees, investors, and other stakeholders, potentially leading to increased loyalty, enhanced brand recognition, and improved financial performance. These findings align with the propositions of agency theory, suggesting that sustainability influences financial performance. They are also consistent with the findings of Hope (2020), Yazid et al. (2021), and Abdulrahman et al. (2021). However, they differ from the findings of (Pancawati et al. 2020), Malarvizhi, and Ranjanni (2016).

5.3 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study utilized net profit margin, return on assets, and return on capital employed as key indicators of financial performance.

A comprehensive review of conceptual, theoretical, and empirical literature was undertaken to assimilate insights from prior researchers regarding sustainability reporting and its implications for financial performance. This encompassed an in-depth exploration of the three dimensions of sustainability reporting—economic, environmental, and social disclosures—alongside the fundamental concept of

financial performance. However, the empirical studies surveyed presented divergent results, with some indicating a positive impact while others reported no significant effect. The study grounded its theoretical framework in legitimacy theory.

For the research methodology, an ex-post facto design was adopted, and secondary data were sourced from the annual financial statements of thirteen publicly listed oil and gas marketing companies on the Nigeria Stock Exchange as of the year-end 2022. Utilizing purposive sampling techniques, a sample of five oil and gas companies was selected. The data spanned a five-year period from 2010 to 2022. Diagnostic tests were conducted to ensure data validity and determine the appropriate model for the study. STATA 13 statistical software was employed for data analysis, involving both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study's hypotheses were tested based on the results obtained, which indicated that sustainability disclosure has a positive and significant impact on net profit margin, return on assets, and return on capital employed.

5.4 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusion and are recommended:

- i. Enhance sustainability reporting: Given the positive impact of sustainability disclosure on NPM and ROA, organizations should make it mandatory to report sustainability practices. This involves collecting and reporting comprehensive data on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors relevant to their operations and stakeholders. Clear and transparent reporting can help build trust with investors, customers, and other stakeholders, potentially attracting capital and enhancing the company's reputation.
- ii. Align sustainability goals with financial objectives: Companies should integrate sustainability goals into their overall strategic planning and ensure alignment with financial objectives, particularly NPM and ROA. By recognizing the potential positive effects of sustainability on financial performance metrics, organizations can adopt a holistic approach that considers both short-term profitability and long-term sustainability. This alignment can lead to improved decision-making, resource allocation, and risk management, ultimately driving financial gains.

5.5 Suggestion for Further Research: This study focused on investigating the impact of sustainability disclosure on the financial performance of listed oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria. Future researchers are encouraged to expand this line of inquiry by incorporating additional variables to provide a more comprehensive understanding of sustainability disclosure. Additionally, exploring the reciprocal relationship and investigating whether financial performance influences sustainability reporting is a valuable avenue for further research. Examining these aspects will contribute to a more holistic understanding of the dynamics between sustainability disclosure and financial performance in the context of the oil and gas industry in Nigeria.

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